

Supporting Information for

Microenvironment tailoring for electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction: Effects of interfacial structure on controlling activity and selectivity

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Experimental Methods

NAMs preparation

Superhydrophobic nanowire arrays with microgrooves (NAMs) were fabricated on Cu foil using a two-step double-pass anodic alumina oxide (AAO) template-assisted electrodeposition method. The Cu foils (99.999% purity, 0.2 × 20 × 10 mm) used in the experiments were polished with 800, 1500, 2000, 3000, and 5000 mesh sandpaper in sequence. After mechanical polishing, it was electropolished in 85% phosphoric acid at 3 V against a counter electrode for 1 min. Before utilization, the Cu foil was supersonically cleaned with acetone, ethanol, and deionized water for 5 min in sequence and then dried with nitrogen gas. A schematic illustration of the custom-made setup for the first step of electrodeposition is shown in Supplementary Fig. 1. The plating solution was composed of copper pyrophosphate ($\text{Cu}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Sigma–Aldrich), potassium pyrophosphate ($\text{K}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Sigma–Aldrich), ammonium citrate tribasic ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_7$, Sigma–Aldrich, 97%), and deionized water (Milli-Q, >18 M Ω cm) with a mass ratio of 6:25:2:100. A double-pass AAO template (Bonding Chemical) wetted with electroplating solution was placed on Cu foil. A filter paper completely wetted by the plating solution was placed on the AAO template to store the plating solution. The counter Cu foil was placed over the filter paper to form a 2-electrode system. The first step of electrodeposition was carried out at -0.8 V for 60 min. In the second step, electrodeposition was carried out in a single cell with three electrodes for another 60 min. The applied potential was -0.8 V vs. Ag/AgCl. After electroplating, the cathode was rinsed and immersed in 2 M NaOH (Sigma–Aldrich, 98%) solution for 3 hours to completely dissolve the AAO template. The Cu nanowire arrays were obtained after being washed with deionized water and dried with nitrogen gas. Finally, the hydrophobic functionalization of NAMs was achieved by immersing the as-fabricated sample in a 2.5 mM *n*-octadecanethiol ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{38}\text{S}$, Sigma–Aldrich, 98%) solution (dissolved in ethanol) at 70 °C for 1 h.

Sample characterization

The morphology of the samples was observed by a field-emission transmission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM, JSM-7610F) equipped with an energy-dispersive

spectrometer (EDS, X-Max). The surface wettability was characterized using a contact angle goniometer (Dataphysics, TBU100) at room temperature (25 °C), with the probe liquid being 4 μL of deionized water. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) data were collected on a Kratos AXIS Ultra spectrometer. X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded on a Shimadzu XRD-6000 X-ray diffractometer with a Cu $K\alpha$ source and a Rigaku Miniflex 600 diffractometer.

Electrochemical measurements

The CO_2 electrochemical reduction reaction was carried out in a gas-phase-connected H-type electrochemical cell with a standard three-electrode system connected to a potentiostat (Bio-Logic, VMP-300) for data collection. Each compartment of the H-cell was filled with 40 mL electrolyte (0.1 M KHCO_3) and separated by an anion exchange membrane (AEM, Fumasep FAS-50). Pt foil and Ag/AgCl electrode filled with 3.5 M KCl solution were used as the counter electrode and the reference electrode, respectively. Before the CO_2RR test, CO_2 gas was bubbled into the electrolyte at a flow rate of 20 $\text{mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ for 20 min to saturate the electrolyte with CO_2 . The gas flow rate was controlled at 20 sccm during the test. The cathodic electrodes were placed with a tilt angle of 30° such that the gas bubble flow from the bottom could impact the electrode surface. The electrode potentials were rescaled to the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) with iR compensation using the following equation,

$$E_{\text{RHE}} = E_{\text{Ag/AgCl}} + 0.2046 + 0.0591 \times \text{pH} - IR \quad (1)$$

where I is the current and R is the internal resistance.

The ECSA values were estimated from double-layer capacitance (C_{dl}) currents at different scan rates from 20 to 180 $\text{V}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. The C_{dl} values were achieved by a linear fit of the slope. The ECSA was then determined from the difference between the capacitance of the NAMs relative to that of the Cu foil with a surface area of 1 cm^2 .

CO stripping voltammetry was performed immediately after 40 min of CO_2RR at -1.2 V vs. RHE. CO stripping chronoamperometry (CA) was performed by a 4-step CA sequence for double layer charging correction¹. A schematic illustration of this procedure is also shown in Supplementary Fig. 12. In step I, we performed CO_2RR for 40 min at -1.2 V vs. RHE. During this step, the key intermediate CO^* was produced. In step II, the

potential was switched to 0.2 V vs. RHE for 3 min. In this step, the current included both electrode charging and CO oxidation until CO was depleted. In step III, the potential was switched to -1.2 V vs. RHE again and sustained for 1 s, ensuring that the cathode was charged under the same conditions as in step I. In step IV, the potential was set at 0.2 V vs. RHE for 3 min, under which the current represents the electrode charging solely because negligible CO was produced in a 1 s CO₂RR process. Thus, the difference between steps II and IV represents the net CO stripping current.

Product analysis

Gas-phase products were quantified using a gas chromatograph (GC, Shimadzu, 2014C). Liquid-phase products were detected by a ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectrometer (Bruker, 400 MHz). The FE was calculated based on the following equation,

$$FE(\%) = \frac{n_{\text{product}} \times n_{\text{electrons}} \times F}{It} \quad (2)$$

where n_{product} is the product measured (mol), $n_{\text{electrons}}$ is the number of transferred electrons for the generation of the product, F is the Faraday constant ($\text{C} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$), I is the current, and t is the reaction time for the collected products.

Laser scanning confocal microscopy

The gas–liquid–solid interfaces were directly observed through a series of confocal images at different depths within the nanowire arrays. All measurements were carried out on a laser scanning confocal microscope (Leica, Stellaris 8) equipped with a $\times 63$ water objective lens. Rhodamine B was used as the fluorescent dye for imaging the electrolyte at a concentration of $1 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$. Accordingly, a 540 nm laser was used as the excitation source. The reflection and emission signals were recorded. The confocal images were then obtained by overlaying the reflection and emission signals.

Computational modeling

To clarify the underlying mechanism by which the microscopic wetting state boosts CO₂RR performance, we carried out a three-dimensional and steady-state numerical simulation of the mass transfer process in CO₂RR to determine the distribution of pH, CO₂

concentration, and fluxes of species involved in chemical equilibria within the structure under the applied operating conditions by exploiting the finite-element method on the COMSOL Multiphysics® platform.^{50,51}

In this model, the electroreactions of CO₂RR and HER in 0.1 M KHCO₃ saturated with CO₂ at -1.2 V vs. RHE; the carbonate species equilibria of OH⁻, CO₂, HCO₃⁻, and CO₃²⁻; the mass diffusion of CO₂, OH⁻, H⁺, K⁺, HCO₃⁻, and CO₃²⁻; and the local hydrolysis of K⁺ in the electrolyte phase are considered.

The assumptions involved in this model are as follows: (1) The mass transfer processes are in a steady state, and diffusion occurs near the surface with negligible convection. (2) CO₂RR and HER occur at the liquid–solid interface, and the CO₂RR and HER-induced mass consumption (CO₂) and generation (OH⁻) are presented. (3) Because of the Cassie-Baxter wetting state and the stable CO₂ gas layer underneath the nanowires, a constant concentration condition of saturated CO₂ is at the gas–liquid interface of NAM-30. (4) Due to the partial wetting of NAM-10, *i.e.*, gas layer is underneath the nanowires at some sites and liquid fulfills the nanowires at other sites, we carried out the two different simulations of the above two cases and used the average value for comparison among the different samples. (5) In the NAM-0 model, the electrolyte is filled with nanowires as a result of the Wenzel wetting state.

The governing equation of the mass transfer processes can be described by the Nernst–Planck equation,

$$N_i = -D_i \nabla c_i - z_i \frac{D_i}{RT} F c_i \nabla \phi \quad (3)$$

where the first and second terms represent the mass transfer induced by the concentration gradient and ion migration under the electric field, respectively. At steady state, the governing equations for the different species can be expressed by,

$$\nabla \left(-D_{\text{CO}_2} \nabla c_{\text{CO}_2} \right) = k_{1r} c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} - k_{1f} c_{\text{CO}_2} c_{\text{OH}^-} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \left(-D_{\text{HCO}_3^-} \nabla c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} - z_{\text{HCO}_3^-} \frac{D_{\text{HCO}_3^-}}{RT} F c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} \nabla \phi \right) = \\ k_{1f} c_{\text{CO}_2} c_{\text{OH}^-} - k_{1r} c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} + k_{2r} c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} - k_{2f} c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} c_{\text{OH}^-} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\nabla \left(-D_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} \nabla c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} - z_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} \frac{D_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}}{RT} F c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} \nabla \phi \right) = k_{2f} c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} c_{\text{OH}^-} - k_{2r} c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} \quad (6)$$

$$\nabla \left(-D_{\text{OH}^-} \nabla c_{\text{OH}^-} - z_{\text{OH}^-} \frac{D_{\text{OH}^-}}{RT} F c_{\text{OH}^-} \nabla \phi \right) = k_{1r} c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} - k_{1r} c_{\text{CO}_2} c_{\text{OH}^-} + k_{2r} c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} - k_{2r} c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} c_{\text{OH}^-} \quad (7)$$

To solve the above equations, several boundary conditions are adopted, as shown in Supplementary Fig. 15. Bulk conditions (1), *i.e.*, a constant concentration of species, are considered at the top end of the electrolyte.

$$c_i = \text{cons.} (i = \text{CO}_2, \text{HCO}_3^-, \text{HCO}_3^{2-}, \text{OH}^-, \text{K}^+) \quad (8)$$

Symmetric condition (2), *i.e.*, zero flux of all species, are imposed at the lateral wall of the electrolyte to reflect the periodic 1/6 (60°) of the circumferential nanowire array and the symmetric V-shaped groove.

$$N_i = -D_i \nabla c_i - z_i \frac{D_i}{RT} F c_i \nabla \phi = 0 \quad (9)$$

At the boundaries of the nanowire surface (3), zero-flux conditions are adopted for nonreactive species,

$$N_i = -D_i \nabla c_i - z_i \frac{D_i}{RT} F c_i \nabla \phi = 0 (i = \text{HCO}_3^-, \text{HCO}_3^{2-}, \text{K}^+) \quad (10)$$

while reaction conditions are imposed for CO₂ and OH⁻, which are involved in CO₂RR and HER, respectively. The reactions occurring at the solid–liquid interface can be determined by the Nernst equation and the applied electrode potential,

$$E_{\text{eq}} = E_{\text{eq}}^0 - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left(\frac{c_{\text{OH}^-}^n}{c_{\text{CO}_2}^m} \right) \quad (11)$$

For the CO₂RR, a first-order dependence of the CO₂ consumption rate on the concentration is assumed. Consequently, the boundary condition for consumption of CO₂ at the solid–liquid interface can be expressed by,

$$N_i = -D_{\text{CO}_2} \nabla c_{\text{CO}_2} = k_{\text{CO}_2} c_{\text{CO}_2} \quad (12)$$

The rate constant k_{CO_2} can be obtained by coupling the electron transfer (partial current density of products) and the mass conservation (FE of products) acquired from the experimental results,

$$\left(\frac{j}{F} \right) \sum_k \frac{\text{FE}_k \cdot m_k}{z_k} = \iiint_{l-s \text{ interface}} k_{\text{CO}_2} c_{\text{CO}_2} dx dy dz \quad (13)$$

A zero-order dependence of the OH⁻ generation rate on the concentration is assumed. Similarly, the boundary condition for OH⁻ can be obtained by,

$$N_i = -D_{\text{OH}^-} \nabla c_{\text{OH}^-} = k_{\text{OH}^-, \text{CO}_2\text{RR}} c_{\text{CO}_2} + k_{\text{OH}^-, \text{HER}} \quad (14)$$

The rate constant k_{OH} can be obtained by coupling electron transfer (partial current density of products) and mass conservation (FE of products),

$$\left(\frac{j}{F}\right) \sum_k \frac{\text{FE}_k \cdot m_k}{z_k} = \iiint_{l-s \text{ interface}} k_{\text{OH}^-, \text{CO}_2\text{RR}} c_{\text{CO}_2} dx dy dz \quad (15)$$

$$\left(\frac{j}{F}\right) \frac{\text{FE}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot m_{\text{H}_2}}{z_{\text{H}_2}} = \iiint_{l-s \text{ interface}} k_{\text{OH}^-, \text{HER}} dx dy dz \quad (16)$$

The buffer effect of K^+ near the surface due to the electric potential can be described by,²⁻³

The reactions toward different products detected in experiments and corresponding stoichiometric parameters are given in Supplementary Table 2. The equilibria involving the protonation/ deprotonation of species in solution, the corresponding forward and backward reaction rate constants, and the reaction equilibrium constants are listed in Supplementary Tables 3 and 4, respectively. The diffusion coefficients and bulk concentrations (initial concentrations) for the involved species in the model are listed in Supplementary Table 5.

The set of above equations with boundary conditions forms a closed system for the calculation of the concentrations of all the species involved in the three-dimensional system.

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. The configuration of the electrodeposition. (a) The configuration of the first step electrodeposition. The filter paper and AAO template are saturated with an electroplating solution. (b) The configuration of the second step electrodeposition.

Figure S2. SEM images of AAO templates. The AAO templates are with the same pore pitch of 450 nm and different pore diameters of (a) 200 nm, (b) 300 nm, and (c) 400 nm.

Figure S3. The contact angle measurement of the NAMs and Cu foil before hydrophobic treatment.

Figure S4. X-ray diffraction of the NAMs before and after hydrophobic treatment.

Figure S5. Energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) mapping of NAMs (a) before and (b) after hydrophobic treatment.

Figure S6. Selectivity of (a) NAM10, (b) NAM-0, and (c) Cu foil for CO₂ electroreduction reaction in CO₂-saturated 0.1 M KHCO₃ electrolyte.

Figure S7. Current densities for (a) NAM-30, (b) NAM-10, (c) NAM-0, and (d) Cu foil at various potentials (vs. RHE).

Figure S8. The geometric area normalized partial current density for different samples.

Figure S9. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) curves with various scan rates for (a) NAM-30, (b) NAM-10, (c) NAM-0, and (d) Cu foil.

Figure S10. (a) CO stripping voltammetry of NAM-30 and NAM-0. (b) The zoomed-in CO oxidation peak of (a), which are indicated by triangular markers. CO oxidation (line) and subsequent cycle (dashed) are obtained at a scan rate of 50 mV/s. The CO stripping was performed immediately after a 40 min operation of CO₂RR at -1.2 V vs RHE for each sample.

Figure S11. (a) CO stripping voltammetry normalized by ECSA of NAM-30 and NAM-0. (b) The zoomed-in CO oxidation peak of (a), which are indicated by triangular markers. CO oxidation (line) and subsequent cycle (dashed) are obtained at a scan rate of 50 mV/s. The CO stripping was performed immediately after a 40 min operation of CO₂RR at -1.2 V vs RHE for each sample. (c) Comparison of the peak current density of CO oxidation (j_p) between NAM-30 and NAM-0.

Figure S12. Schematic illustration of the double layer charging correction method for chronoamperometric CO stripping. Step I (40 min): Set potential at -1.2 V vs RHE to perform CO₂RR for producing and accumulating CO at the cathode. Step II (3 min): Change potential to 0.2 V vs RHE immediately, under which potential the current represents both the electrode charging and CO oxidation, until the CO is depleted. Step III (1 s): Change potential to -1.2 V vs RHE immediately, ensuring the cathode is charged and in the same condition with that in step I. Step IV (3 min): Change potential to 0.2 V vs RHE immediately, under which potential the current represents the electrode charging solely as negligible CO is produced in a 1 s CO₂RR process. The difference between step II and IV represents the net CO stripping current.

Figure S13. Chronoamperometric CO stripping at 0.2 V vs RHE for (a) NAM-30 and (b) NAM-0. The shaded area represents the net CO stripping current.

Figure S14. Net CO stripping current density after double layer correction for (a) NAM-30 and (b) NAM-0 derived from Figure S13.

Figure S15. Boundary conditions illustration. 1-bulk condition, 2-symmetric condition, 3-reaction condition, 4-constant concentration of CO_2 if a gas layer is underneath the nanowires; if there is no gas layer, the bottom liquid–solid interface is the same with boundary 3.

Figure S16. Mass transfer of Cu foil. (a) Contour maps of the concentration profile of CO_2 . (b) Contour maps of pH.

Figure S17. Mass transfer of NAM-10 with a gas layer underneath the nanowires. (a) Contour maps of the concentration profile of CO₂. (b) Contour maps of pH.

Figure S18. Mass transfer of NAM-10 in a completely Wenzel-wetting state. (a) Contour maps of the concentration profile of CO₂. (b) Contour maps of pH.

Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Calculated C_{dl} and ECSA for NAMs.

Sample	C_{dl} (mF/cm ²)	ECSA
Cu foil	0.403	1
NAM-30	0.132	0.327
NAM-10	0.456	1.132
NAM-0	1.000	2.481

Table S2. Reactions considered in the model and corresponding stoichiometric parameters.

Reaction k	CO ₂ (m)	OH ⁻ (n)	e ⁻ (z)
$2 \text{H}_2\text{O} + 2 \text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{H}_2 + 2 \text{OH}^-$	0	2	2
$\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + 2 \text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{CO} + 2 \text{OH}^-$	1	2	2
$\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + 2 \text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{HCOO}^- + \text{OH}^-$	1	1	2
$\text{CO}_2 + 6 \text{H}_2\text{O} + 8 \text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{CH}_4 + 8 \text{OH}^-$	1	8	8
$2 \text{CO}_2 + 8 \text{H}_2\text{O} + 12 \text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_4 + 12 \text{OH}^-$	2	12	12
$2 \text{CO}_2 + 10 \text{H}_2\text{O} + 14 \text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_6 + 14 \text{OH}^-$	2	14	1
$2 \text{CO}_2 + 9 \text{H}_2\text{O} + 12 \text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} + 12 \text{OH}^-$	2	12	12
$3 \text{CO}_2 + 13 \text{H}_2\text{O} + 18 \text{e}^- \rightarrow \text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH} + 18 \text{OH}^-$	3	18	18

Table S3. Equilibria considered in the model and corresponding rate constants.

Equilibria	k_f ($\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)	k_b (s^{-1})
$\text{CO}_2 (\text{aq}) + \text{OH}^- \leftrightarrow \text{HCO}_3^-$	5.93	1.34×10^{-4}
$\text{HCO}_3^- + \text{OH}^- \leftrightarrow \text{CO}_3^{2-} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	10^6	2.5×10^4

Table S4. Equilibria considered in the model and corresponding equilibrium constants.

Equilibria	K_w
$\text{H}_2\text{O} \leftrightarrow \text{OH}^- + \text{H}^+$	10^{-8}
$[\text{K}^+(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n] + \text{H}_2\text{O} \leftrightarrow [\text{KOH}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{n-1}] + \text{H}_3\text{O}^+$	$10^{-8.5}$

Table S5. Diffusion coefficients at 25 °C and bulk concentrations in CO₂-saturated 0.1 M KHCO₃.

Species	D (m ² ·s ⁻¹)	c (mol·m ⁻³)
CO ₂	1.91×10^{-9}	34.2
HCO ₃ ⁻	9.23×10^{-10}	99.7
CO ₃ ²⁻	1.19×10^{-9}	29.4
OH ⁻	5.27×10^{-9}	6.31×10^{-5}
K ⁺	2.056×10^{-9}	99.7
H ⁺	5.27×10^{-9}	1.59×10^{-4}

Supplementary References

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